

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY TO ASSESS THE PERCEPTION ON VOLUNTARY BLOOD DONATION AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN SELECTED NURSING COLLEGE OF MIRZA, KAMRUP, ASSAM

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Abstract-

Background of the study: Voluntary Blood Donation is a self-donating service provided to the sufferers and it is an important factor in the community. The prevalence rate of anemia in adolescent girls (31.3%) & in pregnancy (29.9%), accidents (1130 accidents and 422 deaths every day) are increasing day by day in which people requires amount of blood for survival. There is a failure of blood donors to meet the demand such as after an accident, during surgery, severe disease condition etc.

Material and Methods: A descriptive study was conducted among undergraduate nursing students. Non-probability convenient sampling technique (N=100) was used to pick the study subjects. The study was conducted in NEMCARE Institute of Nursing Sciences, Mirza, by using 5-point Likert scale.

Results/Findings: The study findings revealed that (72)72% students had good perception, (28)28% had moderate perception and none of them had poor perception regarding Voluntary Blood Donation. There is a significant association between perception with demographic variable i.e., types of family.

Conclusion: The study shows that majority of the students have good perception on Voluntary Blood Donation. We have found a significant association between perception with demographic variable i.e., types of family on Voluntary Blood Donation.

Keywords: Voluntary, Blood Donation, Undergraduate nursing students, Perception

INTRODUCTION:

Blood donation is the most important factor in the community. A person, gives blood willingly and receives no payments for it is called Voluntary Blood Donation. It mainly focuses in reducing the unavailability of quality blood. Voluntary Blood Donation program is to implement by Blood Banks, State Blood Transfusion Councils, NGO's. Voluntary Blood Donors are the motivated and desired person to help others for their moral and social responsibility. At National and State level different Blood Council have been set up.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To assess the perception on voluntary blood donation .
2. To find out the association between perception and demographic variable on voluntary blood donation .

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

1. Bhuiyee S.H. et.al. (2022) conducted a descriptive study on factors influencing voluntary blood donation practice among university students of Bangladesh with a sample size of 439. The results showed that blood donation have been done by the students for atleast once and most of the 1st year students more first time blood donors.
2. Getie A et.al. (2021), conducted a cross-sectional study on knowledge of Blood Donation and associated factors in Ethiopia: a systematic review and meta-analysis with a sample size of 8334. Result of the study was over all Nationwide knowledge level was 56.57% . Maximum of the study subjects have the knowledge on blood donation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research Approach: Quantitative research approach.

Research design : Descriptive research design.

Variables:

Demographic variables :The demographic variables in our study are age, religion , educational status, residence and type of family of the students.

Research Variables:The research variable in our study is Perception on Voluntary Blood Donation.

Settings of the study:NEMCARE Institute of Nursing Sciences , Mirza, Kamrup , Assam.

Populations: Undergraduate nursing students.

Target populations: Undergraduate Nursing Students of NEMCARE Institute of Nursing Sciences, Mirza, Kamrup, Assam.

Accessible population: The accessible population for the study were B.Sc. Nursing 2nd Semester , B.Sc. Nursing 2nd year and B.Sc. Nursing 3rd year student who are available at the time of data collection.

Sample size: 100

Sample and sampling technique: Sample were Undergraduate Students in selected nursing college, Mirza, Assam who fulfills the inclusion criteria. Sampling technique for the study was non probability convenient sampling technique.

Criteria for selection of sample:

Inclusion criteria: B.Sc. Nursing students who were willing to participate.

Exclusive criteria : Those students who are not available during the time period of data collection.

Tool and Techniques:

The tool used in this study were:

SECTION-A : Demographic profile , it included

- Age
- Religion
- Educational status
- Residence
- Type of family

SECTION B-: 5 point Likert Scale:

- It consists of 20 statements to assess students perception on voluntary blood donation.

Categorization of perception score:

Poor Perception : 0-33

Moderate Perception : 34-66

Good Perception : 67-100

Validity of the Tool :

The tool along with the problem statement and the objectives was submitted to three experts: Department of Medical Surgical Nursing and Mental Health Nursing. The experts were requested to give their opinion regarding accuracy and appropriateness of the content.

Ethical consideration :

1. Written permission taken from the Principal, NEMCARE Institute of Nursing Sciences, Mirza ,Assam.
2. Verbal and written consent has obtained from the study sample.
3. The subjects were assured of confidentiality of the data obtained.

RESULTS:

TABLE 1 : Frequency and percentage distribution of demographic variables of students
N=100

Demographic variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age		
18-19 years	17	17%
19 – 20 years	27	27%
20-21 years	39	39%
21 years and above	17	17%
Religion		
Hindu	71	71%

Muslim	27	27%
Christian	02	02%
Others	0	0%
Educational Status		
B.Sc. (N) 2 nd Semester	54	54%
B.Sc. (N) 2 nd Year	27	27%
B.Sc. (N) 3 rd Year	19	19%
Residence		
Home	07	07%
Hostel	83	83%
Paying guest	10	10%
Type of family		
Nuclear	94	94%
Joint	06	06%

Fig No.1 : Percentage distribution of level of perception of students regarding Voluntary Blood Donation

Table 2 : Assessment of mean and standard deviation of perception scores among students regarding Voluntary Blood Donation.

N=100

Perception	Score
Minimum Score	50
Maximum Score	100

Median	69
Mean	68.61
Standard Deviation (SD)	4.88

It shows the mean score of perception was 68.61 ± 4.88 . The median value was 69 with minimum score of 50 and maximum score of 100 .

Table 3: Association between level of perception of students regarding Voluntary Blood donation with their demographic variables.

Demographic Variable	Moderate	Good	Chi-square	df	p-value
Age			$\chi^2=4.79^{N.S}$	3	0.187
18-19 years	7.0%	10.0%			
19- 20 years	6.0%	21.0%			
20-21 years	11.0%	28.0%			
21 years and above	4.0%	13.0%			
Religion			$\chi^2=0.534^{N.S}$	2	0.7657
Hindu	20.0%	51.0%			
Muslim	7.0%	20.0%			
Christian	1.0%	1.0%			
Educational Status			$\chi^2=0.558^{N.S}$	2	0.756
B.Sc. (N) 2 nd Semester	16.0%	38.0%			
B.Sc. (N) 2 nd Year	8.0%	19.0%			
B.Sc. (N) 3 rd Year	4.0%	15.0%			
Residence			$\chi^2=0.558^{N.S}$	2	0.984
Home	2.0%	5.0%			
Hostel	23.0%	60.0%			
Paying Guest	3.0%	7.0%			
Type of family			$\chi^2=9.741$ S*	1	0.0018
Nuclear	23.0%	71.0%			
Joint	5.0%	1.0%			

* $p < 0.05$, S =Significant, N.S.=Not significant, df =degree of freedom

CONCLUSION:

The conclusion drawn from the findings of the study is that maximum students have moderate perception i.e., 28.0%, 70.0% had good perception and none of them had a poor perception. Study findings also showed that there is a significant association between demographic variable i.e., types of family and perception on voluntary blood donation among undergraduate nursing students. The present study indicated that the majority of the B.Sc. nursing students have good perception on voluntary blood donation. In future, educational program which could be conducted in hospital or in community level to improve the perception and practice regarding blood donation.

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